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PRINCIPLES OF LIABILITY FOR THE OBLIGATIONS OF A COMMERCIAL-LAW COMPANY: THE EXAMPLE OF A POLISH LIMITED LIABILITY COMPANY

Abstract: *The article addresses the issue of liability for the obligations of a limited liability company according to the rules applicable in the Polish Commercial Companies Code. The article first present the structure of a commercial company, whose pillar is the independence of the company's assets from the assets of its partners. The entity conducting the business activity is the company which is liable for its obligations. The company's shareholders are not liable for the company's obligations. It does not mean that there is no possibility of repaying the creditor if the company does not have assets that would enable it to settle the claim. The Commercial Companies Code provisions envisage the subsidiary liability of members of the company's management board in the event that enforcement against the company's assets turns out to be ineffective. Yet, the liability of the company's management board members is not absolute. They may be released from liability in the cases specified in the Commercial Companies Code, which will be analyzed in this paper. The article will also discuss the principles of liability for the company's obligations in case of absence of the company's management board. The conducted analysis yields a conclusion that, despite the lack of personal liability of the partners of a limited liability company, there are situations that give rise to liability of the members of the body responsible for managing the company's affairs and representing it, who will be liable with their personal assets. The structure of liability for the obligations of a limited liability company adopted by the Polish legislator, based on the principle of subsidiarity, is intended to guarantee honest conduct of business activities.*

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1. Introduction

The Act of 15 September 2000, the Commercial Companies Code,¹ introduced two groups of commercial companies into the Polish legal system. The first group includes partnerships (a registered partnership, a professional partnership, a limited partnership, and a limited joint-stock partnership), and the second group includes capital companies (a limited liability company, a simple joint-stock company, and a joint-stock company). One of the key features distinguishing individual groups of commercial companies is the scope of liability for the company's obligations. In a partnership, emphasis is placed on the personal liability of the company's partners, whose scope is determined by the structure of a specific partnership. In a capital company, as a rule, partners are not liable for the company's obligations.

A commercial law company is established upon entry into the register of entrepreneurs kept by the National Court Register. At that moment, it also obtains separate property and begins a legal existence independent from its partners. It becomes an entity conducting business activity and bearing responsibility for its obligations. Despite many elements common to all commercial companies, a limited liability company is one of the most frequently chosen forms of conducting business activity in Poland. Therefore, this article will be based on the model of responsibility for the obligations of this entity.

This article aims to analyze the legal solutions in Poland, providing the creditor with an effective way to prevent the ineffectiveness of satisfying their claims against a limited liability company. For the purposes of this article, the provisions of the Polish Commercial Companies Code will be examined, providing the basis for holding the members of the management board of a limited liability company personally liable, as well as the principles of liability for the company obligations in the absence of the management board. Next, it will be determined whether, despite the lack of personal liability of the company's partners, the structure of liability in a limited liability company adopted by the Polish legislator, based on the principle of subsidiarity, can constitute a guarantee of fair conduct of business activity by this entity.

2. The structure of liability in a limited liability company

One of the basic principles of a limited liability company's construction is the exclusion of partners' liability for the company's obligations, which is envis-

¹The Commercial Companies Code, *Journal of Laws* of 2024, item 18.

aged in Article 151 §4 of the Commercial Companies Code (hereinafter: the CCC). The exclusion of partners' liability is dictated by the fact that a limited liability company has a separate legal existence from its partners. At the moment the registry court makes an entry in the register of entrepreneurs, a limited liability company is established as a legal entity and acquires legal personality (Article 12 of the CCC). Entry in the register is the last stage in the process of creating a commercial law entity. The first stage of the company's establishment will be the conclusion of the company agreement (Article 163 of the CCC). It is at this moment that a limited liability company in organization is established (Article 161 §1 of the CCC). While waiting for the entry in the register, the capital company in organization may acquire rights, incur obligations, sue and be sued in its own name (Article 11 §1 of the CCC). Liability for obligations incurred in this period is borne jointly and severally by the company and the persons who acted on behalf of the company (Article 13 §1 of the CCC). A shareholder of a limited liability company in organization will be jointly and severally liable with these entities only if he does not contribute to cover the acquired shares in full, and the scope of liability will be determined by the value of the uncontributed endowment (Article 13 §2 of the CCC). Exemption from liability is possible by actually making a contribution in the agreed amount. Making a contribution means transferring ownership of the subject of the contribution to the company's assets, from which enforcement can then be carried out (Kupryjańczyk, 2024, Article 13, Note 9). Upon approval of the actions performed by persons who acted on behalf of the company in the shareholders' meeting, their liability towards the company ceases (Article 161 §3 of the CCC), but not towards third parties. The entry of a limited liability company into the entrepreneurs' register results in the creation of a proper company, which takes over the rights and obligations of its predecessor (Article 12 of the CCC). The liability towards third parties of the company in organization is transferred to the proper company (Frąckowiak, 2017, Article 13).

The consequence of separating the company from its partners is the separation of the company's assets and its full liability for its own obligations. This entity, being a legal person, is liable without limitation with all of its assets. By establishing a limited liability company, the partners assumed the economic risk associated with making contributions to the share capital or other benefits provided for in the company agreement.

The partners will not be liable for the company's obligations also due to the fact that they do not represent the company or manage its affairs. These tasks have been entrusted to the management board (Article 201 §1 of the CCC). Persons who are not management board members may perform specific

activities only on the basis of a power of attorney granted by the company (Article 161 §2 and Article 253 §1 of the CCC). The company representation includes performing activities on behalf of the company related to the subject matter of its activity in external relations, which includes making declarations of intent and appearing before public administration bodies and courts. Managing the company's affairs includes activities performed within the framework of internal relations in the company (Kidyba, 2018, Article 201). It means separating, at least formally, management from capital. In exercising their powers, the management board members benefit from independence from the company's shareholders. However, this independence is not absolute. It is confirmed by the statutory requirement to obtain the consent of the shareholders or the supervisory board to perform specific activities (Article 17 §1-3 of the CCC). The autonomy of the company's management board will also be limited by the right of the shareholders' meeting to command instructions and guidelines to the management board (Article 207 of the CCC). Regardless of the limits on the management board autonomy, the management board members should perform the entrusted duties, taking care of the interests of the company on whose behalf they act.

The right to appoint and dismiss members of the management board has been granted to partners (Article 201 §4 of the CCC), but it will not result in them assuming personal liability for the members' actions. The legislator has also introduced conditions for performing the function of a member of the management board. Only a natural person with full legal capacity can be a member of the management board (Article 18 §1 of the CCC), which excludes the possibility of a legal person performing this function. This person cannot be convicted by a final judgment for the offences specified in Article 18 §2 of the CCC. Partners may also specify additional requirements that candidates for the position of a member of the management board should meet (Article 201 §5 of the CCC). These requirements may be positive (including, among others, education, experience, age, no criminal record) or negative (by introducing a restriction that, for example, a member of the management board cannot be a partner) (Kupryjańczyk, 2024; Article 201, Note 15). The Commercial Companies Code also does not introduce any restrictions as to the possibility of dismissing a member of the management board from the function he/she performs. If there are no provisions in the company agreement limiting the right to dismiss a member of the management board for important reasons (Article 203 §2 of the CCC), he/she may be dismissed at any time by a decision of the shareholders (Article 203 §1 of the CCC).

The provisions of the Commercial Companies Code do not limit a partner in his/her participation in the company. It is possible to combine functions and

a partner may simultaneously be a member of the company's management board, provided that he/she does not perform a competitive activity (Article 211 §1 of the CCC). Any restrictions in this respect may result from the provisions of the company agreement. A member of the company's management board may be a person from among the partners or from outside their group. Combining these competences usually occurs in smaller entities, which usually include two partners, or so-called family companies, connected by members of the closest family. In such cases, the entry of partners into the company's management board allows for saving costs related to the involvement of a third party in the company's structure or building a personal bond with the company. The consequence of appointing the management board members from among the partners will be that the partner will be subject to the regime of the provisions concerning the management board and those relating to partners. In view of this, the status of a member of the management board should be clearly distinguished from the status of a partner. A partner who is a member of the company's management board may be liable for the obligations of a limited liability company on the basis of Article 299 §1 of the CCC. The rule set out in Article 151 §4 of the CCC does not apply to exclusive liability towards the management board members who are also partners of a limited liability company.²

The company's management board acts on behalf of a limited liability company. All liabilities incurred are made in the name and on behalf of the company, which results in the liability of this entity. This means that the company's liabilities should be paid from its assets. Members included in the management board should have the competence to perform the functions entrusted to them in managing the company and be reliable and honest in performing their duties. They are also obliged to properly manage the company's affairs. Incurring liabilities on behalf of the company entails the obligation to perform a prior analysis of the company's capabilities in terms of performing each of them. Lack of proper assessment the company's financial capacity may entail consequences in the form of late payment of receivables, the creation of additional charges in this respect, such as interest for late payment, compensation for the costs of recovering receivables, etc. These consequences may result from mismanagement in decision-making by the management board. The multitude of liabilities incurred in this way may deprive the company of the possibility of performing them. In such a situation, the creditor will be forced to file a lawsuit, which in principle generates additional costs, including the costs of the trial, and then to file an enforce-

² See also: Judgment of the Supreme Court of 14 February 2003, IV CKN 1779/00, *Legalis* No. 58252

ment proceeding. If the company does not have assets that would allow for the satisfaction of the due receivable, enforcement will be impossible, which will result in the ineffectiveness of enforcement against the company.

3. Subsidiary liability

The inability to satisfy a creditor from the company's assets may be an example of mismanagement of this entity. A limited liability company as a legal person may operate only through its representatives, i.e. the management board, which is obliged to look after the company's interests. This approach is based on the provisions of the Commercial Companies Code. They provide a basis for holding a person who is a member of the management board of a limited liability company (members of the management board) personally liable in case the enforcement of the company's assets proves ineffective and there is no action on their part to protect the company from the inability to fulfil its obligations (Article 299 §1 of the CCC). They take vicarious liability for the obligations of the company they represent.

The structure of subsidiary liability referred to in Article 299 §1 of the CCC is intended to motivate the management board members to take due care of the company's interests (Jagodziński, 2018: 44; Szczurowski, 2024, Article 299, Note 1). In case of improper management of the company's affairs (that did not lead to settling the creditor's claim from the company's assets due to the impossibility of effective enforcement), the company's creditor may demand payment of due obligation from the personal assets of the management board members.

The subject of subsidiary liability of management board members will be the obligation incurred by the limited liability company in the course of its operation. This obligation should be of a monetary nature (Kappes, 2009: 60; Szczurowski, 2024, Article 299, Note 2), and the source of its creation may be, among others, an agreement, an act, a tort, or unjust enrichment. The creditor may demand substitute performance of any obligation of the company. The provision of Article 299 §1 of the CCC does not introduce any exclusions in this respect.³ The subject of the obligation of a management board member may also be the costs of the proceedings against the company, the costs of enforcement proceedings,⁴ and interest for late performance of the obligation by the company.⁵ This liability is not limited in amount. There-

³ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 19 October 2005, V CK 258/05, *Legalis* No. 97241

⁴ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 16 March 2007, III CSK 404/06, *Legalis* No. 97708; Judgment of the Supreme Court of 8 March 2007, III CSK 352/06, *Legalis* No. 97711

⁵ Decision of the Supreme Court of 7 December 2006, III CZP 118/06, *Legalis* No. 79166

fore, any default on payment of due obligations by the company generates further costs, which deepens the actual debt.

The liability of the members of the management board, referred to in Article 299 §1 of the CCC, is a subsidiary liability towards the company. This means that they will be liable when enforcement from the company's assets is ineffective. It should be emphasized that the ineffectiveness of enforcement must concern the entire company's assets.⁶ However, there is no need to direct enforcement to assets from which it is unrealistic to satisfy the claim.⁷ In other words, enforcement does not have to be conducted from each asset of the company if the circumstances of a specific case indicate that the company does not have any assets that would allow it to satisfy the debt being collected⁸ (Pabis, 2004: 528).

The demonstration of condition of the ineffectiveness of enforcement against the company rests with the creditor. When initiating proceedings against members of the management board, the creditor should submit evidence of the fact proving this premise. Typical evidence in such circumstances will be a decision to discontinue enforcement proceedings against a limited liability company due to the ineffectiveness of enforcement. However, submitting this decision will not always be sufficient to prove the premise of ineffective enforcement. Having a claim against the company, the creditor is obliged to take actions aimed at effective enforcement of the obligation. The creditor's tardiness in conducting enforcement actions and initiating enforcement proceedings with a delay may not mean that this important premise has been proven, which will result in dismissing the claim against members of the management board.⁹ The Supreme Court took the stance that the company creditor is obliged to take effective actions in order to satisfy its claim from the company's assets. Taking enforcement actions in due time may contribute to a positive conclusion of enforcement proceedings against the company for the creditor.¹⁰

The ineffectiveness of enforcement is variable. After determining the ineffectiveness of enforcement against the company, the creditor may obtain satisfaction from the company's assets. In such a case, there is no basis for assuming that the creditor may exercise the right to demand satisfaction

⁶ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 20 December 2005, II CK 152/05 *Legalis* No. 71727

⁷ Judgment of the Court of Appeal in Łódź of 29 January 2014, IACa 1370/13, *Legalis* No. 1023986

⁸ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 7 July 2007, V CK 19/05, *Legalis* No. 94580

⁹ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 24 April 2004, III CK 107/03, *Legalis* No. 65956

¹⁰ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 16 November 2011, V CSK 515/10, *Legalis* No. 453517

from the assets of the management board members. He would then act to the detriment of the management board members of the debtor company. It is worth emphasizing, however, that for the justification of the claim under Article 299 of the CCC, the decisive factor is the financial status of the debtor company existing at the time of closing the trial against the management board members. The management board members may be liable with their own assets only for such obligations of the limited liability company that cannot be satisfied from the assets of this entity.¹¹ Pursuing a claim against a management board member will have the nature of a compensatory financial benefit (Kappes, 2009: 60).

Subsidiary liability will also be borne by the liquidators of a limited liability company, except for those established by the court (Article 299 §1 of the CCC). Liquidators perform the same tasks in a limited liability company as members of the management board but during the period of the company's liquidation. In addition, previous members of the management board may become liquidators, and the fact of initiating the company's liquidation proceedings does not exempt them from liability under Article 299 §1 of the CCC.

4. Circumstances excluding the liability of a member of the management board of a limited liability company

Liability under Article 299 §1 of the CCC is the personal and joint liability of members of the management board of a limited liability company. They are liable with their personal assets for the obligations of the company on whose behalf they act. Each member of the management board may be released from liability referred to in Article 299 §1 of the CCC if he/she proves that the declaration of bankruptcy was filed in due time or a decision was issued at the same time to open restructuring proceedings or to approve an arrangement in the proceedings on approval of an arrangement, or that the failure to file the declaration of bankruptcy was not due to his/her fault, or that the creditor did not suffer any damage despite the failure to file the declaration of bankruptcy and the failure to issue a decision to open restructuring proceedings or to approve an arrangement in the proceedings on approval of an arrangement (Article 299 §2 of the CCC).

Fulfillment of at least one of the aforementioned conditions provides a member of the management board with grounds for exemption from liability. The construction of the provision of Article 299 §2 of the CCC allows for the assumption that a member of the management board of a debt limited liability company may be exempted from subsidiary liability only if he/she takes action to protect the financial interests of the creditor.

¹¹ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 22 February 2008, V CSK 421/07, *Legalis* No. 108783

The first circumstance releasing a member of the management board from subsidiary liability is the filing of the declaration of bankruptcy. It should be emphasized, however, that the act of filing a declaration itself does not release the company's management board from liability because the condition for exoneration is to perform this act in due time. The very moment of filing the declaration will depend on the specific situation. The period should be counted differently in the case of a member of the management board who has only just taken up a function on the management board as compared to the one who has held the function for some time. Nevertheless, it will be the specific member of the management board who will be responsible for demonstrating the grounds for his/her lack of liability.¹² The concept of due time is a subject matter of doctrine and case law alike. Yet, it seems reasonable to support the view prevailing in the doctrine, which requires referring to the norms of bankruptcy law when defining this concept. Pursuant to Article 21 §1 of the Bankruptcy Act (2003),¹³ an application for bankruptcy should be filed by the debtor (limited liability company) within 30 days from the occurrence of the grounds for declaring bankruptcy. In case of taking up the function of a member of the management board at a later date, the 30-day period should be counted from the date of taking up the function¹⁴ (Kappes, 2004: 514).

Considerations regarding the definition of the concept of the proper time will also be relevant in the case of the second exoneration circumstance, which is the issuance in due time of a decision on the opening of restructuring proceedings or on the approval of an arrangement in the proceedings on the approval of an arrangement. The opening of restructuring proceedings will constitute a basis for releasing a member of the management board from liability under Article 299 §2 of the CCC only if it is made within 30 days from the date on which the basis for its opening occurred. It should be emphasized that the decision in this respect is issued by the bankruptcy court, and a member of the management board of a limited liability company has no influence on the date of issuing such a ruling. Therefore, it seems that burdening the management board with the requirement to obtain a decision on the opening of restructuring proceedings or on the conclusion of an arrangement in the proceedings on the approval of an arrangement within a specified time is an obligation that is almost impossible to fulfill. The management board of the company does not have any legal instrument to force the court to issue a judgement. It, therefore, seems reasonable to rephrase the content of this

¹² Decision of the Supreme Court of 30 January 2019, III CZP 78/18, *Legalis* No 1870558

¹³ The Act of 28 February 2003 - Bankruptcy Act, *Journal of Laws* of 2004, item 794

¹⁴ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 30 September 2004, IV CK 49/04, *Legalis* No 80190

exoneration premise and replace it with the obligation to submit a restructuring application in due time (Szczurowski, 2022: 182).

The third exoneration premise is the lack of fault of the member of the management board in failing to file the declaration of bankruptcy of the company. Only a member of the management board who is not at fault may be exempted from liability, and it will be irrelevant whether the declaration of bankruptcy was filed at all (Pabis, 2004: 532). However, it seems that proving the lack of fault in failing to file a declaration remains difficult in practice. Under Article 209(1) §1 of the CCC, each member of the management board is obliged to exercise due diligence resulting from the professional nature of their activity and remain loyal to the company when performing their duties. Therefore, the lack of fault of a member of the management board may only occur in exceptional cases, which include, among others, a long-term illness preventing them from performing their duties, or failure to disclose information concerning the company (Rachwał, 2007: 1037). The division of duties between individual members of the management board and not dealing with financial matters cannot constitute grounds for excluding guilt, which would exempt them from substitutive liability (Kappes, 2009: 295; Szczurowski, 2024, Article 299, Note 51).

The last exoneration premise is the lack of damage to the creditor despite the failure to file the declaration of bankruptcy and the failure to issue a decision on opening restructuring proceedings or the failure to approve the arrangement in the proceedings on approval of the arrangement. Damage is specifically defined under Article 299 §2 of the CCC. This provision assumes a presumption of the existence of damage. The lack of damage on the part of the creditor will mean that the failure to file a bankruptcy petition or to initiate arrangement proceedings did not affect the creditor's ability to satisfy his/her claim from the assets of the limited liability company (Szczurowski, 2024, Article 299, Note 52).

All grounds for the exoneration of liability listed in Article 299 §2 of the CCC are related to the conduct of a management board member, and aimed at protecting the interests of the creditors of a limited liability company, which could prevent the harm to creditors or at least reduce the amount of debt.

5. Lack of a body authorized to represent and manage the company's affairs

The scope of the subsidiary liability for the obligations of a limited liability company is specified in Article 299 §1 of the CCC. This provision precisely indicates that this liability is borne by members of the management board.

Yet, it does not limit the possibility of filing a claim for damages only to members of the management board on the day the creditor makes this claim, covering members of the company's management body in a broad sense.

A member of the company's management board is a person appointed to perform this function in line with the provisions of the Commercial Companies Code and the provisions of the company's agreement. Thus, the provision of Article 299 §1 of the CCC will apply to persons who were formally appointed to the company's management board, even if in fact they never performed this function.¹⁵ It has been emphasized in case law that courts cannot accept the practice of fictitious appointment of so-called figureheads to the management board, which would lead to avoiding the consequences of the lack of satisfaction of the company's creditors. Given that such a person consciously and voluntarily agreed to such a state of affairs, there is no basis for excluding their liability for the company's incorrect economic decisions that led to the company's indebtedness, even if they did not make these decisions themselves. The person appointed to the company's management board is obliged to monitor the company's debt (at least), thus enabling the board members to make the right decisions in due time, i.e. to file a bankruptcy petition or take steps to open restructuring proceedings or to approve an arrangement.¹⁶ The provision of Article 299 §1 of the CCC will not apply to persons who actually perform tasks falling within the competence of the company's management board but were not formally appointed to this function,¹⁷ nor to a member of the company's management board performing this function for less than 30 days (Article 21 of the Bankruptcy Act).

When starting cooperation with a company, a prospective creditor should be vigilant and subject the commercial law entity which it intends to cooperate with to verification. The protective function of a potential creditor may be performed by the register of entrepreneurs kept by the National Court Register¹⁸ (hereinafter: the NCR), which lists all commercial law companies and, among others, persons who are members of the individual company bodies. Based on the data disclosed in the register of entrepreneurs of the NCR, the creditor may assess whether the person who is to sign the agreement is a member of the company's management board or its proxy. Although the pro-

¹⁵Judgment of the Court of Appeal in Warsaw of 26 March 2021, VII AGa 1482/18, *Legalis* No 2584117

¹⁶Judgment of the Court of Appeal in Kraków of 24 November 2021, I AGa 139/20, *Legalis* No 2680817

¹⁷Judgment of Court of Appeal in Katowice of 20 December 2001, I ACa 886/01, *Legalis* No 54612

¹⁸Act of 20 August 1997 on the National Court Register, *Journal of Laws* of 2024, item 979

visions of the Commercial Companies Code require the conclusion of specific types of agreements by the company's proxy (Article 210 §1 of the CCC), as a rule, the management board should conclude the agreement on behalf of the company. The prospective creditor should verify the reasons for concluding the agreement by the proxy, in the absence of a statutory order. This will allow to determine whether the company's management board consists of persons actually representing the company or a so-called figurehead. Thus, a creditor may make a well-informed decision on entering into cooperation with such an entity.

Members of the management board are liable from the moment of their appointment until the expiry of their term of office. The fact of entering or deleting a member of the management board from the register of entrepreneurs is irrelevant to liability under Article 299 §1 of the CCC due to the declarative nature of this entry (Siemiątkowski, 2007: 222, Szczurowski, 2024, Article 299, Note 57). Importantly, this liability is borne by all persons who held the position of a member of the company management board from the date of the occurrence of the obligation¹⁹ if an application for declaring bankruptcy of the company was filed at that time (Szczurowski, 2024, Article 299, Note 58) until the date of declaring bankruptcy or dismissing the application in this respect.²⁰ However, those members of the management board who did not file a declaration of bankruptcy at the time of the enforcement proceedings conducted by foreclosure or by sale of the company will not be held liable if the obligation to file such a motion arose during the enforcement proceedings (Article 299 §4 of the CCC).

It should be emphasized that a member of the management board may be held liable only if he/she held the position after the obligation arose, even if it was not yet due (Karolak, 2006: 98), until the enforcement was found to be ineffective (Dyczkowski, 1994: 22). Thus, persons who became the company management board members after the enforcement was found to be ineffective are not liable for the company's obligations because they did not hold this position at the time when these obligations were incurred.²¹ Resignation from the position of a management board member or a member's dismissal by the partners does not exclude their fault or their liability. The fact that a given person was a member of the management board during the aforesaid period is significant for the validity of the claim, even if their term of office has already expired, if they have been dismissed or if they have resigned from the position. The fact that, on the date of filing such a claim,

¹⁹ Decision of the Supreme Court of 28 February 2008, III CZP 143/07, *Legalis* No 94054

²⁰ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 31 January 2007, II CSK 381/06, *Lex* No 327921

²¹ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 14 April 2016, IV CSK 485/15, *Legalis* No 1460760

the company does not have a body authorised to represent it and manage its affairs is also irrelevant to the subsidiary liability for damages of a member of the company's management board.

The compensatory nature of the claim against the members of the management board of a limited liability company determines that the creditor has the right to file a claim against the members of the management board of the debtor company until the expiry of the limitation period for the claim, which is 20 years in this case (Article 442(1) §2 of the Civil Code).²² The period should be counted from the day on which the creditor learned of the ineffectiveness of enforcement against the company or, with due diligence, could have learned about it, provided that the creditor himself took active and immediate action in the process of recovering the debt from the company (Szczyrkowski, 2024, Article 299, Note 68).

6. Conclusions

A limited liability company is one of most frequently chosen business structures for conducting business activity in Poland. It is a capital company where partners are not liable for its obligations. The structure of a limited liability company does not provide grounds for satisfying the creditor from the personal assets of the company's partners in case of inability to enforce payment from the company's assets. However, it does not mean that persons acting on behalf of the company may incur obligations without prior verification of the company's ability to fulfill such an obligation. The legal structure of a limited liability company adopted in Poland does not allow for incurring obligations with impunity. The provisions of the Commercial Companies Code allow for holding members of the management board of a limited liability company liable when enforcement against the company's assets proves ineffective. Members of the company's management body bear subsidiary liability for the obligations of a limited liability company when enforcement against the company proves ineffective, and there are no grounds for releasing a member of the company's management board from liability for its obligations, referred to in Article 299 §2 of the CCC.

The structure of solutions adopted by the Polish legislator aims to ensure protection of the creditor against dishonest conduct of business activity. However, the liability of the management board members for the obligations of a limited liability company is not automatic. It is necessary to file a separate claim for payment against members of the management board of the company, the legal basis of which is the provision of Article 299 §1 of the

²²The Act of 23 April 1964, Civil Code, *Journal of Laws* of 2024, item 1061

CCC. A creditor may file a claim for damages against the management board members of the debtor company only after an ineffective enforcement has been carried out against the debtor company's assets. The possibility of holding the the company management board members liable for its obligations is also determined by the conduct on the part of the creditor. Delay in taking legal actions to enforce the payment due to the company may constitute a negative premise for the subsidiary liability of the company management board members.

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**НАЧЕЛА ОДГОВОРНОСТИ ЗА ОБАВЕЗЕ ПРИВРЕДНОГ ДРУШТВА:
ПРИМЕР ПРИВРЕДНОГ ДРУШТВА СА ОГРАНИЧЕНОМ
ОДГОВОРНОШЋУ У ПОЉСКОЈ**

Резиме

У раду се разматра питање одговорности за обавезе друштва са ограниченом одговорношћу у складу са одредбама пољског Законика о привредним друштвима. Представиће се власничка структура привредног друштва, чији је стуб независност имовине привредног друштва од имовине њених партнера. Привредно друштво је субјекат који обавља делатност и преузима одговорност за своје обавезе. Акционари друштва нису одговорни за обавезе друштва, што не значи да не постоји могућност исплате повериоца уколико привредно друштво нема имовину из које може намирити потраживања. Одредбе Законика о привредним друштвима предвиђају супсидијарну одговорност чланова управног одбора друштва у случају неефикасног извршења (намирења) из имовине привредног друштва. То не значи да је одговорност чланова управе друштва апсолутна. Они могу бити ослобођени ове одговорности у случајевима који су експлицитно наведени у Законику о привредним друштвима, који ће бити предмет анализе. Аутор такође разматра принципе одговорности за обавезе привредног друштва у случају одсуства управног одбора друштва. На основу извршене анализе може се извести закључак да, иако нема личне одговорности партнера друштва са ограниченом одговорношћу, постоје ситуације које доводе до одговорности чланова органа надлежног за вођење послова друштва и његово заступање, који одговарају својом личном имовином. Структура одговорности за обавезе друштва са ограниченом одговорношћу у пољском законодавству, заснована на принципу супсидијарности, има за циљ да гарантује часно руковођење пословним активностима.

Кључне речи: друштво са ограниченом одговорношћу, одговорност за обавезе привредног друштва, начело супсидијарности, основ за ослобађање од одговорности.

